

USING DYNAMIC SIMULATION TO EXPLICITLY TEACH CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS IN CHEMICAL ENGINEERING PROBLEM-SOLVING

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Abstract

There is no argument over the importance of critical thinking, regardless of which field of study. In chemical engineering, critical thinking skills are crucial in troubleshooting plant problems or making design changes, as one must think through the impact of making a change in one parameter (such as temperature) on other parameters (pressure, flow rate, composition, level, etc). Teaching critical thinking, however, proved to be a challenge to many faculty. The task was not made any easier by the plethora of critical thinking models that had been proposed over the years.

In this paper, we presented a practical critical thinking model that we adopted in our teaching. We first briefly explain our past works on instilling critical thinking in our students, and explained how it led us to the decision to explicitly teach critical thinking. We discussed the work done in integrating the critical thinking model into our curriculum; and also presented preliminary results of student experience and performance in using the model. Possible future work based on available literature findings to further strengthen students' skill in practicing critical thinking is also discussed.

Keywords: *Dynamic simulation, chemical engineering, critical thinking, meta-cognition*

Introduction and Brief Summary of Past Works

Critical thinking skills are considered to be invaluable "generic" skills in education. Across universities and disciplines, one finds multiple definitions for critical thinking and different approaches to practicing it. In reality, critical thinking "looks" different in different contexts because the focus must be adapted for each purpose (Bobrowski and Cox, 2007). There are a number of useful quick reviews on the topic in the literature (see for example, UMUC, 2006) as well as websites (see for example, The Critical Thinking Community, at www.criticalthinking.org). Despite the acknowledged importance, unfortunately these critical thinking skills are frequently not taught explicitly, the assumption being that students will learn from the implicit values buried deep within our teaching philosophies (Hargreaves and Grenfell, 2003).

In an earlier paper, the authors had presented specific context of critical thinking in chemical engineering as follows (Cheah and Phua, 2009):

- Ability to compare and contrast the differences in various process variables (temperature, level, pressure, flow rate, composition) in a chemical process plant resulting from a disturbance in stable operating condition or due to equipment malfunction
- Ability to make inferences and interpretations from the above using relevant theories and concepts
- Ability to link together the various observed phenomena and offer plausible explanations of what had happened in the plant

In that paper, the authors explained the use of dynamic simulation in inculcating such critical thinking behaviors among students. The results showed that students in general appreciated the use of dynamic simulation as a learning aid in their studies.

An important area that requires student to make extensive use of critical thinking is the study of HAZOP. In a subsequent study, the author used dynamic simulation as a teaching aid to help students learn the HAZOP technique (Cheah, 2010). The design of the learning process is modeled using the Kolb cycle of experiential learning, as shown in Figure 1. Briefly, Kolb's model has learners working through four phases, which are ideally iterative, Learners start by engaging in a situation (concrete experience, CE), then they observe their behavior and reflect on it (RO). From this, they generalize and develop abstract concepts (AC), which they then return to the field to test by applying them to new situations (AE).

Figure 1. Kolb's Cycle of Experiential Learning

Several learning points had emerged from this study, the most important of which is the need to actively engage students in the practice of reflecting on their thinking during the process (that is, the RO component of the Kolb learning cycle). Critical thinking is of such importance that Wagner (1997) proclaimed that “no one can develop expertise in any area without engaging in the effortful processes of thinking.” We therefore needed a working model that can effectively teach critical thinking to our students.

Towards a Working Model for Critical Thinking

A review of the literature showed that there are many models available. For example, some of the familiar ones include Edward de Bono's Six Thinking Hats and Tony Buzan's Mind Maps. In the engineering context, the often quoted thinking model is that by Richard Paul (see for example, Niewoehner, 2006). Indeed, it could be argued that the plethora of perspectives and terminology tend to confuse rather than aid educational planning and, in particular, teaching. What we needed for our work is a model of thinking that was both valid and practically useful for chemical engineering. In fact, Beyer (1988) went further as to say that:

It is better to include a few important thinking skills processes in a system for teaching thinking skills than to include so many that the result is too much confusion for both teacher and student. (p.15)

Each of the different views and models of what constitutes “critical thinking” brings with it a preferred pedagogy intended as the most likely approach for developing the skills within students (French and Tracey, 2008). For our purpose, we used a model introduced by Dennis Sale, senior education advisor from Singapore Polytechnic, as shown in Figure 2. This model, identifies six main types of thinking which we typically employ in solving problems. These types of thinking are dynamically related and can be used simultaneously in unison.

Figure 2. Sale's Model of Thinking

This model is selected for its ease of use and its ability to explain in clear and systematic manner the thinking processes one utilizes when troubleshooting chemical process plant operations. The model makes explicit the tacit heuristics used by a typical chemical engineer. Being able to contextualize the model in its application is of utmost importance, as the processes of thinking are inexplicably intertwined with the content of thought (that is, domain knowledge). As noted by Willingham (2007):

You can teach students maxims about how they ought to think, but without background knowledge and practice, they probably will not be able to implement the advice they memorize. ... Knowing that one should think critically is not the same as being able to do so. That requires domain knowledge and practice.

Table 1 summarizes the key heuristics that underlie these broad classification frames on different types of thinking.

Table 1.
Summary of Key Heuristics of Types of Thinking

Generating Possibilities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate many possibilities • Generate different types of possibilities • Generate novel possibilities
Compare & Contrast <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify what is similar between things - objects/options/ideas, etc • Identify what is different between things • Identify and consider what is important about both the similarities and differences • Identify a range of situations when the different features are applicable
Analysis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify relationship of the parts to a whole in system /structure/model • Identify function of each part • Identify consequences to the whole, if a part was missing • Identify what collections of parts form important sub-systems of the whole • Identify if and how certain parts have a synergetic effect
Inference & Interpretation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make meaning of information / data available • Identify causal relationships • Identify key points and emphasis • Make predictions concerning future possibilities • Separate fact from opinion • Identify intentions and assumptions
Evaluation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decide on what is to be evaluated • Identify appropriate criteria from which evaluation can be made • Apply the criteria and make decision
Meta-Cognition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aware that we are thinking in a planned manner • Actively thinking about the ways in which we are thinking

- Monitoring and evaluating how effective we are thinking
- Seeking to make more effective use of the different ways of thinking and any supporting learning/ thinking strategies /tools

Note that one need not start with generating possibilities as the starting point during the thinking process. Depending on the situation that requires thinking, one of the thinking processes may be better suited as the starting point. A good thinker is therefore one who is able to use all these types of thinking effectively, quickly and strategically.

Also, in introducing the model, we have adopted the same approach based on the CDIO framework that we had used in the past 3 years (Cheah 2009; Cheah and Sale 2010); that is by integrating it into a suitable core chemical engineering module, instead of teaching it separately in a standalone module. Although a summary by Cotton (1991) had earlier shown that available research seems inconclusive which approach is better; a later study by Hatcher (2006) concluded that an integrated approach to teaching critical thinking give better results than standalone courses.

Description of Work Done

A core module in Year 2, entitled *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention*, is selected to integrate the explicit teaching of the model of thinking depicted earlier. The module is a natural choice for this purpose, as we had previously used dynamic simulation to aid HAZOP learning. The module hours were increased from 45 to 60 hours to accommodate new contents, which besides technical ones, also include the explicit teaching of critical thinking skills. The relevant section of the module syllabus is shown in Table 2. Note that we had made explicit in the learning outcomes that students must be able to apply the critical thinking model in problem solving. As noted by Sale (2007), there is little opportunity to infuse much thinking into the curriculum if the objectives are largely written in terms of ‘define’, ‘list’, ‘state’ or ‘describe’.

Table 2.
Learning Outcomes for Critical Thinking

7	Use Critical Thinking in Process Troubleshooting
7.1	Explain the role of thinking in problem solving.
7.2	Explain the model of critical thinking.
7.3	Explain the importance of meta-cognition in improving thinking.
7.4	Apply critical thinking and problem solving skills on a process trouble-shooting case study.

The use of the model is first illustrated using a non-technical financial investment example that everyone can understand. To make it less stressful and maximize the understanding of the concepts, it was conducted in a light-hearted manner. For the technical part, once again, we used the EnVision dynamic simulation system and

developed two new exercises based on the Flash Drum model shown in Figure 3. The choice of model is also deliberate. This is part of our effort at curriculum integration consistent with our CDIO implementation initiative; whereby students are exposed to the same case or model or plant over and over in different modules during the course of their 3-year study in the Diploma in Chemical Engineering; during which the module-specific chemical engineering principles are employed for teaching and learning.

Figure 3. Flash Drum for Critical Thinking Model

The Flash Drum model has been used in Year 1 in the module *Chemical Engineering Principles and Simulation*. This served to provide the necessary CE component of the Kolb’s learning cycle. We now continue with the learning cycle in the module *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention*. Specifically, in the current exercises, the lecturer guides the students through the use of the various components of the critical thinking model to help troubleshoot problems associated with the Flash Drum operation. It is worth highlighting that the above-mentioned exercises were introduced before students are taught the topic of HAZOP. The intention is to ascertain if the explicit use of a critical thinking model helped students in their understanding of the topics and able to perform better in the HAZOP assignment.

The most important component stressed during the exercises is that on meta-cognition. This is the RO step of the Kolb learning cycle, and serves to strengthen students’ understand of the learning process. Flavell (1976) describes meta-cognition in these words:

Meta-cognition refers to one’s knowledge concerning one’s own cognitive processes or anything related to them, e.g. the learning-relevant properties of information or data. For example, I am engaging in meta-cognition if I notice that I am having more trouble learning A than B; if it strikes me that I should double check C before accepting it as fact.

In short, meta-cognition is the ability to think about one’s own thinking. The rationale is simple: As thinking is a discipline and as such calls for changes in the way we carry out our daily activities and make decisions, we

require a consciousness of our thoughts. In other words in order for students to think about what they are doing they need to be encouraged into a discipline of questioning, and reflecting on their thoughts and thought processes and content. As students become more skilled at using meta-cognitive strategies, they gain confidence and become more independent as learners. Independence leads to ownership as students realized they can pursue their own intellectual needs and discover a world of information at their fingertips. As noted by Winn and Snyder (1996):

Meta-cognition enables learners to monitor their progress as they learn, and make changes and adapt their strategies if they perceive they are not doing so well.

As students improved on their thinking, they become better able to develop knowledge about how to carry out future process troubleshooting challenges (i.e. the AC component of the Kolb learning cycle). Eventually, they are able to extend the knowledge gained in one area to troubleshoot problems in different scenarios (i.e. the AE component on the Kolb learning cycle), especially in later year of study.

In the Flash Drum exercises, the lecturer created a malfunction in the plant operation, the exact nature of which is unknown to the students; who are required to identify it using the critical thinking model. The lecturer systematically takes the students through the entire troubleshooting process, using the model's vocabulary. Examples of application are shown in Table 3.

Table 3.
Examples of application of critical thinking skills

Thinking	Example
Compare & Contrast	Which parameters (flow, level, etc) have changed, which have not?
Inference & Interpretation	Why has it not changed at all? Why has it increased in value but returned to normal later?
Generating Possibilities	Could it that the heat exchanger malfunctioned?
Analysis	If so, what are the signs (e.g. readings) that support this?
Evaluation	Will the hot oil exiting the exchanger tubes become hotter?
Meta-Cognition	Why didn't I consider monitoring the tube outlet temperature?

The new syllabus was introduced in April 2011. To effectively teach the module, special training workshop was conducted for the lecturers involved. The importance of training for lecturers cannot be understated for two reasons: (1) lecturers themselves may not even know how to think critically, and therefore their analysis of the level of critical thinking among students may be limited by their own ability of thinking critically (Black, 2005); and (2) various research had shown that there is a positive relationship

between teacher training and student achievement (see for example, a summary by Cotton, 1991).

In this case, the author worked closely with a senior education advisor from the Department of Educational Development (EDU) to prepare a customized workshop for the lecturers. First the senior education advisor introduces the critical thinking model, as well as the underlying research about how the human brain functions and stores information. Later the author augments the training with applications of the model to critical thinking in chemical engineering problem solving.

Evaluation of Student Learning and Performance

For this pilot study we would like to know if students find the model useful, and if the model is easy to use. We also would like to ascertain if their understanding of critical thinking is consistent with what we expected. In a sense, we would like to ascertain the workability of our present approach before embarking on the more ambitious goal of assessment the students' critical thinking skills. We are mindful of the multiple definitions of critical thinking that had resulted in multiple approaches to assessing critical thinking. As noted by Ennis (2001), critical thinking assessment requires that we be clear about what we are trying to assess. Bers (2005), for example, had briefly discussed various standardised instruments for measuring critical thinking. As noted by Stein et al (2009), it is difficult to find effective tools for assessing critical thinking skills, claiming that many of the assessment tools are plagued by problems related to validity, reliability, and cultural fairness.

The students were surveyed on their understanding of critical thinking at the beginning of the semester; and again after the model is introduced (somewhere in the middle of the semester) and used in several problem-solving examples. These two stages served as the pre-test and post-test stages of our evaluations.

The usefulness of this comparison is derived from the works of Chenault and Duclos-Orsello (2008) who asserted that ... "what our students thought of when they heard *us* use the term critical thinking in our classrooms and course materials, but also how *they* defined or used the term independent of any meanings we assigned to it. We hypothesized that (1) individual students might have multiple responses to the simple request to "define critical thinking", (2) that students in the same classroom might not understand or use the term in the same way, and (3) that students' definitions might not mirror those of a given faculty member or discipline. We imagined that if such variations or contradictions existed so too would there exist challenges for students charged with engaging in critical thinking activities or demonstrating critical thinking skills."

We ask the following open-ended questions during the pre-test evaluation:

- (1) *In your own words, explain what you understand by the word “critical thinking.”*
- (2) *Briefly explain what will you do, if you are asked to solve a problem using critical thinking.*
- (3) *What do you understand by meta-cognition? Explain to the best of your ability.*
- (4) *What do you think are some barriers to effective thinking?*

For the post-test evaluation, we also surveyed the students on the usefulness of the model in helping them develop critical thinking skills. The survey comprises a combination of open-ended questions and several ranking questions using 5-point Likert scale ranging from ‘1’ for Strongly Disagree to ‘5’ for Strongly Agree. The questions are as follows:

- (1) *I am able to use the critical thinking model in completing the troubleshooting exercises.*
- (2) *I find that the critical thinking model is easy to use.”*
- (3) *In order to improve my own thinking skills, it is important for me to frequently review my own thinking process.*
- (4) *I am confident that I am able to use the model for other problem-solving challenges.*
- (5) *List one difficulty you faced in carrying out the troubleshooting exercises. Elaborate on your answer.*

A total of 53 students responded to the pre-test survey, representing a response rate of 91.4%. The result showed that in general students have varying notion of critical thinking, ranging from thinking logically and systematically to out-of-the-box thinking. Only 3 out of the 53 respondents are able to articulate what meta-cognition is. The students also identified a host of factors as barriers to thinking, including closed mindset and poor external environment.

The post-test results are shown in Table 4, where 50 out of 58 students responded, for a response rate of 86.2%. From the data, it can be seen that in general many students are still rather uncomfortable (Q.2) with using the thinking model, although they (marginally) agreed that they are able to use the model to complete the classroom exercises (Q.1). A similar rating was obtained when asked if they are able to use the model for other problem-solving challenges (Q.4).

Table 4.
Students responses to survey questions

Question Number	Student Rating (%)					Average Score
	1	2	3	4	5	
1	2.0	8.0	34.0	56.0	0.0	3.44
2	0.0	8.0	54.0	36.0	2.0	3.32
3	0.0	0.0	22.0	62.0	16.0	3.94
4	0.0	8.0	40.0	48.0	4.0	3.48

Lastly, it is worth noting that more students are now aware that they need to improve on meta-cognition in order to improve their overall thinking process (Q.3).

Discussions and Ideas for Future Work

The first thing we noted is that more time is required on the lecturer’s part to coach the students in using the model during problem solving, e.g. making sense of information sources, evaluating their problem-solving strategies; and in particular, discussing with them on how they are thinking, making their thinking visible to them so they can see what they are doing well and where gaps may be evident, etc; i.e. meta-cognition.

Direct modeling of meta-cognitive thinking by lecturers is an important area that we think needs further improvement. The process is useful in making explicit to students the mental operations involved and how they contribute to the effectiveness of the overall thinking process. As noted by Mimbs (2005):

Teachers need to model critical thinking skills to their students and explicitly teach them to think critically. Teachers can be transformed in their teaching and students can be transformed in their learning through continued, consistent use and application of critical thinking skills.

This is supported by Mandernach et al (2009) who noted that the “key to the success of a discussion in fostering students’ higher-order thinking strategies is the instructor’s interactivity in leading the discussion. Instructors who actively engage their students via a more critical exploration of course concepts are more successful in promoting students’ critical thinking than those instructors who take a more passive role in their teaching.”

We also noted that teaching critical thinking in a single module of *Plant Safety & Loss Prevention* is not sufficient to instil in students the right mindset. We need other lecturers to use the same model in other modules to reinforce what is being taught in the pilot module. As noted by Marzano (1988):

... we can improve students’ ability to perform the various processes by increasing their awareness of the component skills and by increasing their skill proficiency through conscious practice. (p.65)

Hence, in the near term, we would therefore need to encourage widespread use of the critical thinking model in other core chemical engineering modules, to beef up the various components of the Kolb cycle. Given the different interpretations of critical thinking, it is of utmost importance that every lecturer has the same understanding of what constitute critical thinking in the context of chemical engineering process operations; so that everyone can speak the same language and model

the behavior in a consistent way. The findings of Paul, Elder and Bartell (1997) on faculty understanding of critical thinking is most telling in this regard, whereby although an overwhelming majority (89%) of university faculty claim that the promotion of critical thinking is a primary objective of their instruction, yet only a minority (19%) are able to provide a working definition of the concept.

To this end, we want to highlight that dynamic simulation is not the only tools that one can use to inculcate the desired critical thinking skills among students. Other software, even simple Microsoft Excel is useful, especially as a tool to assist in the number crunching needed to generate various solutions in scenario ("what if") analysis to be used in evaluating the effect of various operating parameters on the proposed design.

Next, we also like to know if students performance in troubleshooting process plant malfunction had improved as a result of using the model, compared with an earlier cohort who was not taught the model. In particular, we are interested in knowing if students ability to conduct a HAZOP process is improved with the use of the model.

In the longer horizon, we would like to be able to assess students' ability to practice critical thinking in various engineering tasks. Years of experience in teaching had convinced us that what gets assessed gets learnt. As Ramsden (1992) points out:

From our students' point of view, assessment always defines the actual curriculum Assessment sends messages about the standard and amount of work required, and what aspects of the syllabus are most important. (pp.187-188)

However, as cautioned by Llyod and Bahr (2010), there is subtle difference in how critical thinking was made manifest in individual practice although there appears to be little difference in the intent and content of the definitions offered by academics and students. They noted that academics appeared concerned with disposition and processes of critical thinking; while students can be said to be more concerned with products, i.e. outcomes of critical thinking. This is supported by Choy and Cheah (2009), who pointed out that thinking logically and being able to problem solve using new approaches may not be indicative of critical thinking but may just be the process the student undertakes to gain understanding of the material presented, or as we may add, to complete the assignment as pass the examination.

Lastly, there is also a recognition that critical thinking instruction must also address student dispositions. It is not enough to teach students the skills of critical thinking if they are not inclined to use them. Critical thinking is thus more than the successful use of the right skill in an appropriate context. It is also an

attitude or disposition to recognize when a skill is needed and the willingness to exert the mental effort needed to apply it (Halpern, 1999). Facione (2007) went further to state that "the ideal critical thinker can be characterized not merely by her or his cognitive skills but also by how she or he approaches life and living in general." This is perhaps the ultimate goal that we would like to aim for, as we progress along the journey of equipping our graduates with lifelong learning skills embodied in our holistic education framework.

Conclusions

This paper presented our work in curriculum redesign to explicitly teach students critical thinking skills using a model of thinking. Preliminary findings indicate that more needs to be done to improve student acceptance of the thinking model and their effectiveness in using it in their course of study.

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